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**ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF INNOVATIVE
PROJECT COOPERATION
PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP**

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INTRODUCTION

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY. The interaction of business and government is the key to the effectiveness of rebuilding the national economy. The purpose of the study is justified as analyzing the state of innovative project activity of public-private partnership.

RESEARCH METHODS. The analysis of the state of innovative joint project activity was based on the use of statistical analysis methods, grouping, the method of structural-logical analysis and graphics to demonstrate the results.

PRESENTATION OF THE MAIN MATERIAL. The experience of developed countries of the world and the analysis of the state of innovative project cooperation prove that the form of interaction "state-business" can ensure the successful implementation of projects in the

AND sectors of the national economy. However, there is a need to implement measures to eliminate obstacles to the activation of public-private partnership and, accordingly, the formation of institutional support for this process in the conditions of martial law and the post-war reconstruction of the economy of Ukraine.

RESULTS. The prospects for research in the direction of developing public-private partnership processes are the development and implementation of effective tools and mechanisms of interest of state institutions in the implementation of this type of joint activity.

KEYWORDS: interaction; public-private partnership; innovation; investment attractiveness; sustainable development; cooperation; joint activities; cooperation; concession agreements; partnership relations.

NUMBER OF REFERENCES	NUMBER OF FIGURES	NUMBER OF TABLES
18	0	10

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АНАЛІЗУВАННЯ СТАНУ ІННОВАЦІЙНОЇ ПРОЄКТНОЇ КООПЕРАЦІЇ ДЕРЖАВНО- ПРИВАТНОГО ПАРТНЕРСТВА

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ВСТУП І МЕТА ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ. Взаємодія бізнесу і влади є запорукою ефективності відбудови національного господарства. Мету дослідження обґрунтовано, як аналізування стану інноваційної проектної діяльності державно-приватного партнерства. **МЕТА** існує необхідність впровадження заходів з усунення перешкод активізації державно-приватного партнерства та відповідно, формування інституційного забезпечення даного процесу в умовах воєнного стану та післявоєнної відбудови економіки України.

МЕТОДИ ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ. РЕЗУЛЬТАТИ. Аналізування стану інноваційної спільної проектної діяльності базувалося на використанні методів статистичного аналізу, групування, методу структурно-логічного аналізу та графічного для демонстрування результатів. **РЕЗУЛЬТАТИ.** Перспективами досліджень в напрямку розвитку процесів державно-приватного партнерства є розроблення та впровадження дієвого інструментарію та механізмів зацікавленості державних інституцій у реалізації такого виду спільної діяльності.

ВИКЛАД ОСНОВНОГО МАТЕРІАЛУ. Досвід розвинутих країн світу, та проведений аналіз стану інноваційної проектної кооперації, доводить, що форма взаємодії «держава-бізнес» може забезпечити успішну реалізацію проектів у галузях національної економіки. **КЛЮЧОВІ СЛОВА:** взаємодія; державно-приватне партнерство; інновації; інвестиційна привабливість; сталий розвиток; співпраця; спільна діяльність; кооперування; концесійні договори; партнерські відносини.

Introduction. A promising form of interaction of public-private partnership (hereinafter PPP) provides the possibility of implementing large-scale and high-value projects, establishing long-term partnerships between business and government, sharing risks between project participants, implementing modern technical solutions and innovations, ensuring effective management of newly created facilities, and involving the private sector in the implementation of socially significant projects and development policies (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2021).

Problem statement. Thus, as of January 1, 2023, 193 PPP agreements were concluded, of which nine concession agreements, five joint activity agreements, and four other agreements are being implemented, and the rest (162 agreements) are not being implemented: 116 are not being implemented, 46 are terminated, and 13 are suspended due to the armed aggression of the Russian Federation (Ministry of Economy of Ukraine, 2025).

Unresolved parts of the problem The state of PPP implementation in Ukraine has improved somewhat. Contracts concluded under PPP terms, which are being implemented as of 01.01.2025, amounted to 22 units, including 22 contracts in the Kyiv region. Comparative statistical analysis and its graphical presentation are shown in Table 1 and Fig. 1 (Ministry of Economy of Ukraine, 2025; Brekharia, 2018).

Table 1

Status of PPP implementation in Ukraine. Contracts concluded under PPP terms that are being implemented, 2021, 2023, 2025

Contracts concluded under PPP terms, which are implemented as of 01.01.	2021	2023	2025
Contracts concluded under PPP terms and conditions that are being implemented	24	18	22

Source: based on (Ministry of Economy of Ukraine, 2025; Brekharia, 2018).

If we follow the status of the number of contracts concluded under PPP terms and implemented as of 01.01.2025 by region, the largest number of them is in Kyiv region – 4, including in the healthcare sector – 2 (Table 2).

Analysis of literary sources. Despite the fact that the Law "On Public-Private Partnership" (VRU, 2010) was adopted in 2010, and in 2019 – the new Law "On Concession" (VRU, 2019), there has been no significant spread of this form of interaction between business and government over the past 13 years.

Ukrainian scientists emphasize a significant number of problems in cooperation between business and government, namely: a high level of overregulation of economic activity (over 50 thousand regulatory legal acts); instability of government policy; unsatisfactory quality of the business climate; ineffective regulation of the sphere of natural monopolies; insufficient level of protection of intellectual property; ineffective interaction with tax authorities;

lack of prerequisites for formalizing relations between government and business; imperfection of the institution of legal and moral and ethical norms of business participation in political decision-making processes that affect economic development. On the other hand, 80.1% of businesses do not interact with local authorities or communities, and 94.1% of businesses do not know whether they are included in support programs (Naboka, 2023).

Table 2

Contracts concluded under PPP terms, which are being implemented as of 01.01.2025 by region

Contracts concluded under PPP terms, which are implemented as of 01.01.2025	Tourism, leisure, recreation, culture and sports	Water collection, purification and distribution	Production, transportation and supply of heat and distribution and supply of natural gas	Others	Healthcare	Waste management, except collection and transportation
Volyn	1					
Dnipropetrovsk		2				
Zhytomyr			1			
Transcarpathian		1	2			
Zaporizhzhia		1		1		
Ivano-Frankivsk	1					
Kyiv	1	1			2	
Kirovohrad	1					
Lviv		1				
Mykolaiv		2				
Odesa						1
Poltava						1
Khmelnyskyi				1		
Chernihiv			1			

Source: based on (Ministry of Economy of Ukraine, 2025).

Presentation of the main material. An example of an innovative public-private partnership project cooperation is the corporation NASHE.VSE, a farming cooperative that unites small private farms, which are mainly located in the Kyiv region (NASHE.VSE, n.d.b).

Among them:

- cheese production farm, Tarashchansky district, Makovetskyi farm, Kyiv region;
- quail farm "Zhar-ptytsia", Kyiv region.
- mini-cheese production workshop – cheeses with mold and young cheeses, Knyazhychi village near Kyiv;
- eco-farms Mother, Mali Lysivtsi village, Kyiv region
- craft cheese factory "Syroman", Kyiv region;

- cheese factory "Kozulya", Kyiv region;
- cheese factory village Lemeshivka, Yagotynskyi district, Kyiv region
(Main Department of Statistics in Kyiv Region, n.d.).

This is an incomplete list of farms that have united and sell their products in the city. Kyiv, as well as in other regions of the country. Their products are presented on the website of the corporation NASHE.VSE, a farmer's cooperative on the Internet (NASHE.VSE, n.d.b).

6 principles that formed the basis of the activity and implementation of the mission:

- Only Ukrainian products;
- Only small and medium-sized farms;
- Only proven quality;
- Only an honest product;
- Only a fair price;
- Only responsible consumption (NASHE.VSE, n.d.b).

Unfortunately, for a detailed, in-depth study and research of the production and financial indicators of these business entities, as representatives of innovative project cooperation of public-private partnership, there is not enough statistical information, therefore, the analysis of the state of innovative project cooperation of public-private partnership will be carried out by analyzing the state of enterprises by types of economic activity with a division into large, medium, small and micro enterprises of the Kyiv region, using the statistical collection of 2023 (KURKUL, 2023).

The number of operating enterprises by types of economic activity with a division into large, medium, small and micro enterprises for 2023 is presented in Table 3.

As we can see from the statistical information, the largest number of enterprises in the Kyiv region is small-scale ownership 17,020 units, 94.5%, small enterprises in the agricultural sector 2,069 units, 94.5% of the total number of operating enterprises of the corresponding type of activity. The following is an analysis of the number of employees at enterprises by type of economic activity with a division into large, medium, small and micro enterprises for the studied period (Table 4).

Using Table 5, we will analyze labor costs at enterprises by type of economic activity, divided into large, medium, small, and microenterprises for the period under study.

The next observation is the volume of products sold (goods, services) by enterprises by type of economic activity with a division into large, medium, small and micro enterprises for 2023 (Table 6).

Table 3

Number of operating enterprises by type of economic activity with division into large, medium, small and micro enterprises, 2023

	Total, units	Including							
		large enterprises		medium-sized enterprises		small businesses		of which microenterprises	
		units	in % to the total number of operating enterprises of the corresponding type of activity	units	in % to the total number of operating enterprises of the corresponding type of activity	units	in % to the total number of operating enterprises of the corresponding type of activity	units	in % to the total number of operating enterprises of the corresponding type of activity
Total	18009	37	0,2	952	5,3	17020	94,5	14429	80,1
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	2190	6	0,3	115	5,2	2069	94,5	1740	79,5

Source: based on (KURKUL, 2023).

Table 4

Number of employees at enterprises by type of economic activity with a division into large, medium, small and micro enterprises, 2023

	Total, people	Including							
		large enterprises		medium-sized enterprises		small businesses		of which microenterprises	
		people	in % to the total number of employed workers in the relevant type of activity	people	in % to the total number of employed workers in the relevant type of activity	people	in % to the total number of employed workers in the relevant type of activity	people	in % to the total number of employed workers in the relevant type of activity
Total	284201	54671	19,2	138967	48,9	90563	31,9	36986	13
Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	34725	κ	κ	κ	κ	11418	32,9	4022	11,6

Source: based on (KURKUL, 2023).

Table 5

Labor costs at enterprises by type of economic activity with a breakdown into large, medium, small and micro enterprises, 2023

	Total, thousand UAH	Including							
		large enterprises		medium-sized enterprises		small businesses		of which microenterprises	
		thousand UAH	in % of total labor costs for the relevant type of activity	thousand UAH	in % of total labor costs for the relevant type of activity	thousand UAH	in % of total labor costs for the relevant type of activity	thousand UAH	in % of total labor costs for the relevant type of activity
Total	59539187,5	18855908,6	31,7	30232938,9	50,8	10450340	17,5	3219644,7	5,4
Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	6419764,9	κ	κ	κ	κ	1307946,1	20,4	309285,8	4,8

Source: based on (KURKUL, 2023).

Table 6

Volume of products sold (goods, services) by enterprises by type of economic activity with a division into large, medium, small and micro enterprises, 2023

	Total, thousand UAH	Including							
		large enterprises		medium-sized enterprises		small businesses		of which microenterprises	
		thousand UAH	in % to the total volume of products sold (goods, services) of the relevant type of activity	thousand UAH	in % to the total volume of products sold (goods, services) of the relevant type of activity	thousand UAH	in % to the total volume of products sold (goods, services) of the relevant type of activity	thousand UAH	in % to the total volume of products sold (goods, services) of the relevant type of activity
Total	876287549,7	342945962,9	39,1	349843129,3	39,9	183498458	21	55536114	6,3
Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	71255490,3	κ	κ	κ	κ	19393990,7	27,2	4754005,7	6,7

Source: based on (KURKUL, 2023).

Taking into account the chosen topic of analyzing the state of innovative project cooperation of public-private partnership, it is possible to present the number of operating business entities by type of economic activity of the Kyiv region, since individual entrepreneurs are subjects of public-private partnership and cooperation (Table 7).

Table 7

Number of operating business entities by type of economic activity, 2023

	Total, units	Including			
		enterprises		individual entrepreneurs	
		units	as a percentage of the total number of operating enterprises	units	as a percentage of the total number of active individual entrepreneurs
Total	124761	18009	100	106752	100
Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	3438	2190	12,2	1248	1,2

Source: based on (KURKUL, 2023).

As can be seen from the statistical reporting, individual entrepreneurs in the agricultural sector of the Kyiv region account for 1.2% of the total number of operating individual entrepreneurs in the Kyiv region, that is, a low percentage. Table 8 presents the financial results before taxation of enterprises by type of economic activity, divided into large, medium, small and micro enterprises for 2023.

Table 8

Financial results before taxation of enterprises by type of economic activity with division into large, medium, small and micro enterprises, 2023

	Financial result (balance) before tax, thousand UAH	Businesses that made a profit		Enterprises that suffered losses	
		in % to the total number of enterprises	financial result, thousand UAH	in % to the total number of enterprises	financial result, thousand UAH
1	2	3	4	5	6
Total	53990105,40	74,20	71720694,00	25,80	17730588,60
by large enterprises	32131807,30	78,40	35203868,00	21,60	3072060,70
by medium-sized enterprises	12149086,80	74,10	21760169,80	25,90	9611083,00
by small enterprises	9709211,30	74,20	14756656,20	25,80	5047444,90
including micro- enterprises	1746741,00	72,30	4974481,20	27,70	3227740,20
agriculture, forestry and fisheries	6064230,90	77,40	8623666,10	22,60	2559435,20

End Table 8

1	2	3	4	5	6
by large enterprises	2752593,00	83,30	3438002,00	16,70	685409,00
by medium-sized enterprises	664356,20	71,90	2069847,20	28,10	1405491,00
by small enterprises	2647281,70	77,80	3115816,90	22,20	468535,20
including micro-enterprises	725176,40	76,00	962818,80	24,00	237642,40

Source: based on (KURKUL, 2023).

As we can see, the largest percentage among agricultural enterprises in the Kyiv region that made a profit is large agricultural enterprises 83.30%, followed by small enterprises 77.80%. The largest percentage of losses among medium-sized enterprises is 28.10%, and the smallest losses were incurred by large enterprises 16.70%.

The result of the activities of enterprises is the profitability indicator, the profitability of operating and all activities of enterprises in the Kyiv region for 2023 is shown in Table 9.

Table 9

Profitability of operating and overall activities of enterprises in the Kyiv region by type of economic activity, 2023

	The level of profitability of operating activities of enterprises	The level of profitability of all enterprise activities
Total	12,40	8,00
Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	11,70	7,60

Source: based on (KURKUL, 2023).

We observe positive indicators of profitability of enterprises in the Kyiv region for the studied period, despite the difficult political and economic situation. And finally, in this block of research and analysis of the state of innovative project cooperation of public-private partnership, we will present the value of non-current and current assets, equity and liabilities of enterprises in the Kyiv region by type of economic activity for 2023, as components of the effective activity of business entities (Table 10).

Table 10

Non-current and current assets, equity and liabilities of enterprises by type of economic activity, 2023

	Asset		
	Non-current assets	Current assets	Non-current assets held for sale and disposal groups
Total	347398344,70	565483797,80	267109,50
Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	46730425,30	90112040,30	38334,10

Source: based on (KURKUL, 2023).

Conclusions and prospects of the study. As a result of this study, it should be noted that agricultural enterprises need a model for the development of public-private partnership in the innovation sphere, which would ensure the continuity of the chain "business – science – state" and would allow the formation of a national innovation system. Institutional support for public-private partnership processes will create conditions for the real involvement of private business in the sphere of innovation activity and will form competitive advantages of business entities in the long term.

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